

320 patients of children admitted to the hospital for treatment of mycoplasma pneumonia from June 01, 2018 to January 01, 2023 were collected as the subjects of this study.

Inclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria

Tracheobronchial combination diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic criteria for lobar pneumonia

Inclusion Exclusion Criteria and Diagnostic Criteria We screened a total of 212 cases of compliant samples. Among them, 170 cases of patients with lobar pneumonia were used as the pneumonia group in this study, and 42 cases of patients with tracheobronchial tuberculosis combined with Mycoplasma pneumoniae were used as the combined group in this study.

Xgboost

Decision Trees

Lasso

Logistics

Receiver operating characteristic curve

Precision and Recall

Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator